

Impact of International Public Sector Accounting Standard (Ipsas) Adoption on Financial Accountability and Transparency in Nigeria

Afolabi, Rukayat Toyin, Adegbola, Muritala Makinde

Department of Accounting, Redeemer's University Ede, Osun State, Nigeria

Salami, Ibraheem Oladeji

Department of Management and Accounting, Lead City University, Ibadan, Oyo State, Nigeria

Oladejo, Abiola Hakeem

Department of Accounting, FRSC, Osogbo, Osun State, Nigeria

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ABSTRACT

The current study used a few federal MDAs in Oyo State as case studies to assess the accountability effects of adopting the International Public Sector Accounting Standard (IPSAS) in government establishments. This project's goals are to evaluate how the International Public Sector Accounting Standard (IPSAS) affects public fund transparency in government organizations and how it affects public fund accountability in government organizations. A survey research design was used in this study. Using a basic random selection method, respondents were chosen from the ten (10) federal MDAs in Ibadan, Oyo state. The Federal Road Safety Corps (FRSC) Ibadan, the National Directorate of Employment (NDE), and the Consumer Protection Agency (CPC) are a few of them. There were 110 employees selected, 11 from each of the ten federal (MDA) agencies. The basic data used in this study came from a questionnaire. The data gathered from primary sources was analyzed using the Wilcoxon statistical test tool. According to the study's conclusions, the implementation of international public sector accounting standards has significantly impacted Nigerian government organizations' accountability and openness. This means that the implementation of IPSAS is anticipated to raise the level of accountability and transparency in Nigeria's public sector, as well as to give decision-makers access to more useful information and enhance the country's financial reporting system. However, the study's findings show that IPSAS adoption is anticipated to raise the level of accountability and transparency in Nigeria's public sector, as well as to contribute to the provision of more useful information for decision-makers and to the improvement of the country's financial reporting system.

1. INTRODUCTION

Globally, financial reporting standards have been devised and established in each country's territory based on historical data. However, as globalization has increased cross-national cooperation, trade, and business, there is an urgent need for further harmonization in the rules governing financial statements so that these statements remain understandable and deliver the same information to users everywhere (Ogbuagu and Onuora, 2019). For public sector financial reporting, the requirement for unified accounting standards has been the main impetus behind worldwide public sector accounting standards.

Almost every day brings reports of widespread public sector corruption. The developing world is where this is especially true. Particularly in the West African subregion, there have been numerous reports of widespread misuse of public finances in recent years (Atuilik and Hussein Salia, 2019). The Police Pension scandal in Nigeria; the \$1.6 million bulletproof BMW car fraud involving the Nigerian Aviation Ministry; the N40 billion (roughly US\$308 million) pension scam in Nigeria; and the failure of the state to account for a third of the 84 billion leones (roughly £12 million) set aside to fight the deadly Ebola virus in Sierra Leone are the most recent reported cases of public sector corruption (Ademola et al., 2017).

Accountability in the face of mistrust and dishonesty in the management of public funds is a serious issue that has afflicted the Nigerian public sector. Most successive federal, state, and local administrations have consistently emphasized the problem of corruption, misappropriation, and non-accountability (Ademola et al., 2017). Despite the existence of numerous laws and relevant institutions in Nigeria, the number of reported cases of misappropriation of public funds and properties has significantly increased (Ademola et al., 2017)

As public finance management becomes more transparent and accountable, most governments around the world have resolved to reform their government financial management systems and processes (Ademola et al., 2017). The International Public Sector Accounting Standard (IPSAS) was adopted as the centerpiece of a global accounting revolution and in response to calls for greater government financial accountability and transparency.

The International Federation of Accountants (IFAC, 2012; 2014) introduced IPSAS through one of its standard-setting boards, the International Public Sector Accounting Standard Board (IPSASB), in response to increasing calls for greater transparency and accountability in the management of public funds in the aftermath of the global financial crisis (IFAC, 2017, Schaik, 2018). International Public Sector Accounting Standards (IPSAS) are currently at the center of a global accounting revolution in response to calls for greater government financial accountability and transparency (Ogbuagu and Onuora, 2019).

Following the global financial crisis, the International Federation of Accountants (IFAC, 2012; 2014) introduced IPSAS through one of its standard-setting boards, the International Public Sector Accounting Standard Board (IPSASB) (IFAC, 2017, Schaik, 2018). International Public Sector Accounting Standards (IPSAS) are at the forefront of a global accounting revolution in response to calls for increased government financial accountability and transparency (Ogbuagu and Onuora, 2019).

The International Federation of Accounting (IFAC) body with the authority to develop and issue IPSAS is the IPSASB. According to John (2011), the IPSAS Board has 18 members, 15 of whom are nominated by IFAC member bodies, and the remaining three are appointed as public members by any individual or organization. The primary goal of IPSAS is to improve the quality of general-purpose financial reporting in the public sector, allowing for better evaluation of government resource allocation as well as increased transparency and accountability (Ogbuagu and Onuora, 2019).

In Nigeria today, the ineffectiveness of accounting policies has hampered the country's drive for improved public sector performance and accountability. Accountability in the Nigerian public sector has declined over time as a result of regulatory authorities' negligence and maladministration, as well as a complete disregard for efficient financial reporting (Akinbuli, 2013). Noncompliance with standard financial reporting procedures has become the norm in the majority of Nigeria's public sectors, culminating in a lack of probity, accountability, and prudence with the emergence of deficiencies such as unpaid remittances, improper record processing, indiscriminate printing, and use of revenue records and receipts, to name a few (Adaramola, 2015).

The ineffective audit system had eroded the efficiency of the public sector in Southwest Nigeria, with no or little reflection of lapses in audit reports over the years, despite the gravity of misappropriation and mismanagement of public funds, which had previously incapacitated most states in Nigeria, particularly Kogi, Osun, Oyo, and Ekiti. Few empirical studies on public sector accountability focused on assessing the level of financial control and financial accountability in the country's public sector, citing the role of International Public Sector Accounting Standards, the level of corruption, the implications of international public sector accounting standards on financial accountability in the Nigerian public sector, and the fiscal dilemma on financial accountability (Ijeoma, 2016; Balo, 2016).

Previous empirical studies have found a low level of accountability and the need for an effective control system in the country's public sector. IPSAS ensures high standards, which act as a catalyst for the preparation of sound and transparent financial statements. As a result, operational performance, accountability, and resource allocation become more efficient (Ademola et al., 2017). Indeed, IPSAS is used to provide accurate and comprehensive accounting information in order to demonstrate a high level of accountability, stewardship, and credibility. This study aims to investigate the impact of IPSAS adoption on financial accountability in selected federal MDAs in Oyo State was used as a case study in order to gain a better understanding of IPSAS and its implications for public sector accounting

1.1. Statement of the Problem

The adoption of IPSAS has recently sparked a debate about whether it will aid in ensuring accountability and transparency in the Nigerian public sector. Scholars who have researched the subject believe that implementing IPSAS will improve accountability and transparency, whereas others believe that implementing IPSAS will have a negative impact on public sector accountability due to the cost of implementation.

Previous research has produced contradictory and mixed results. For example, Ijeoma (2015) claims that implementing IPSAS will improve the reliability, credibility, and integrity of government financial reporting, whereas Okeke (2015) claims that implementing IPSAS will have a negative impact on public sector accountability due to the high cost of such implementation. As a result, empirical evidence on the implications of IPSAS on public sector accountability has been inconsistent and inconclusive, which is what the current study seeks and addresses.

1.2. Objectives of the Study

The overall goal of the research is to evaluate the impact of IPSAS on the financial accountability of selected federal MDAs in Oyo State. While the study's specific objectives are as follows:

- i. Investigate the impact of IPSAS adoption on accountability in the Nigerian public sector
- ii. Determine whether the use of IPSAS improves transparency in Nigeria's public sector.

1.3. Research Questions

The following questions would be addressed in this study:

- i. How far has the implementation of IPSAS improved accountability in the Nigerian public sector?
- ii. How far has the implementation of IPSAS improved transparency in the Nigerian public sector?

1.3. Hypotheses of the Study

The study formulated and tested the following hypotheses:

Ho₁: Adoption of IPSAS has had no discernible impact on accountability in the Nigerian public sector.

Ho₂: Does the adoption of IPSAS have any effect on transparency in the Nigerian public sector?

2. METHODOLOGY

2.1. Research Design

The study employed a survey research design to collect data on the accountability implications of IPSAS adoption in public sector governance. Structured questionnaires distributed to the intended respondents were used to collect data from primary sources. The study's goal was to identify ministries, departments, and agencies (MDAs) in the public sector that generate a lot of money. This study included both fully and partially funded MDAs. However, the study was limited to MDAs in Oyo state, which is located in Nigeria's South-West region.

2.2. Area of Study

This study was carried out in Ibadan, Oyo State. This is because the headquarters of all selected parastatals (MDAs) are in Ibadan.

2.3. Population of the Study

The population for this work is made up of ten (10) selected MDAs in Ibadan, Oyo State. These parastatals were purposefully chosen for the survey due to their headquarters' location in Ibadan, as well as Ibadan's status as Oyo state's economic hub.

2.4. Sample size and Sample Technique

The population of the study includes all employees of the Federal (MDAs), which include the Nigeria Postal Service, Ibadan, the University of Ibadan, the National Youth Service Corps (NYSC), Oyo state secretariat, the Federal pay office, the Standard Organization of Nigeria (SON), the Central Bank of Nigeria (CBN), the Consumer Protection Agency (CPC), the National Directorate of Employment (NDE), and the Federal Road Safety Corps (FRSC) Ibadan. One hundred ten questionnaires were distributed and administered to selected MDA staff members, with eleven distributed to each of the aforementioned MDAs in Ibadan, Oyo state.

2.5. Method of Data Collection

In order to gather information on the impact of TSA on public fund management, a structured questionnaire was distributed to respondents in the selected MDAs. The questions were created with a five-point Likert scale in mind: strongly agree, agree, undecided, disagree, and strongly disagree.

2.6. Research Instrument

Primary data for the study was collected using questionnaires. A questionnaire was used to gather critical information about the impact of IPSAS adoption on accountability in the Nigerian public sector. Closed-ended questions were used so that respondents could select one of the researcher's predefined categories. It not only clarifies the question's meaning for respondents, but it also encourages them to respond quickly. In addition, the answers are much easier to code and analyze. The questionnaire had two sections: demographics and the mode of accountability and transparency in the governance of Nigerian public-sector organizations. The independent variables that were assumed to influence governance were accountability and transparency. The Likert scale was used to assess these variables.

2.7. Validity and Reliability of Research Instrument

The instrument (questionnaire) used for data collection was validated by experts in accounting and other related fields of research, and the external consistency method was used to determine the instrument's reliability. The test was conducted with 5% of the sample size, which is 6. Six copies of questionnaires were used for this test, which was administered to six people in Ibadan, along with an introductory letter stating and emphasizing the study's basis. The results were compiled, and the sample size was re-tested after two weeks. The six copies of the questionnaire were all retrieved for the first test. The results of the retest correlated with the results of the previous test, confirming the reliability of the tests. The questionnaires were distributed to 110 respondents from Ibadan, Oyo State, who works for the ten selected Federal (MDAs). 100 questionnaires were completed, returned, and analyzed correctly.

2.8. Method of Data Analysis

The questionnaire was analyzed using simple frequency and percentages, and the hypotheses were statistically tested using the Wilcoxon test tool in SPSS V20 at the 5% level of significance.

3. RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

3.1. Administration of Questionnaire

Table1: Questionnaire Distributed, Returned, Rejected and accepted among selected ten Federal (MDAs) in Ibadan, Oyo State

S/N	Federal (MDAs)	Questionnaire Distributed	Questionnaire Returned	Questionnaire Rejected	Questionnaire Accepted
1	Nigeria Postal Service	11	11	1	10
2	University of Ibadan	11	11	1	10
3	National Youth Service Corps (NYSC)	11	11	1	10
4	Federal pay office	11	11	1	10
5	National Orientation Agency (NOA)	11	11	1	10
6	Standard Organization of Nigeria,(SON)	11	11	-	11
7	Central Bank of Nigeria (CBN)	11	11	1	10
8	Consumer Protection Agency (CPC)	11	11	2	9
9	National Directorate of Employment (NDE)	11	11	-	11
10	Federal Road Safety Corps (FRSC)	11	11	2	9
	Total	110	110		100
	Percentage	100%	100%	10%	90%

Source: Field Survey 2022

Table 1 depicts the distribution of questionnaires among ten selected federal (MDAs) in Ibadan, Oyo State. There were 110 questionnaires distributed in total, with 11 distributed in each of the federal districts (MDAs). The complete set of ten questionnaires distributed was returned (Table 1). However, 10% of the questionnaires were returned empty-handed due to incomplete filling. Finally, 100 (90%) of the questionnaires were accepted for further interpretation and analysis (Table 1).

3.2. Socio-economic Characteristics of the Respondents

The socioeconomic characteristics listed below were identified and described. age, gender, marital status, annual income, qualifications, and work experience.

Table 2: Socio-economic Characteristics of the Respondents

S/N	CLASSIFICATION	ITEMS	FREQUEN CY	PERCENTA GES	TOTA L
1	Age	Below 30years	31	31	100
		31-40	52	52	
		41-50	12	12	
		Above 50 years	5	5	
2	Gender	Male	65	65	100
		Female	35	35	
3	Marital Status	Married	80	80	
		Single	20	20	
4	Income per annum	Below #5000,000	20	20	100
		Between #500,000 - #1M	21	21	
		#1M - #2M	35	35	
		#2M - #5M	15	15	
		#5M - #5M	9	9	
5	Qualification	SSCE/GCE/O LEVEL	8	8	100
		ND/NCE	25	25	
		HND/B.sc/B.Tech	52	52	
		M. Sc	12	12	
		Ph.D	3	3	
6	Working Experience	Below 1 year	12	12	100
		1-5 years	41	41	
		10 – 15 years	19	19	
		15 -20years	20	20	
		20 -25 years	8	8	

Source: Field Survey 2022

Table (2) shows that 31(31%) of respondents are under the age of 30, 52(52%) are between the ages of 31 and 40, 12(12%) are between the ages of 41 and 50, and 5(5%) are over the age of 50. There are 65 (65%) males and 35 (35% females) among the 100 questionnaires distributed. Eighty percent (80%) of those polled are married, with the remaining 20% being single. According to the income distribution, 20(20%) of respondents earn less than \$500,000 per year, 21(21%) earn between \$500,000 and \$1,000,000, 35(35%) earn between \$1M and \$2M, 15(15%) earn between \$2M and \$5M, and 9(9%) earn between \$5M and \$10M. According to the qualifications of the respondents, 8(8%) have SSCE/GCE/O level results, 25(25%) have ND/NCE, 52(52%) have HND/B.Sc/B.Tech, 12 (12%) have Masters, and 3(3%) have PhD certificates. In terms of work experience, 12(12%) have had less than 5 years, 41(41%) have had 1–5 years, 19(19%) have had 10-15 years, 20(20%) have had 15-20 years, and 8(8%) have had 20–25 years (Table 2). This indicates that the majority of respondents has been spending more than a year and is knowledgeable.

3.3. Effect of IPSAS adoption on accountability in the Nigerian public sector

Table 3: Impacts of IPSAS adoption on accountability of public funds in government organization

S/N	Statement	No. of Respondents/ Percentage (%)				
		SA	A	U	D	SD
1	IPSAS allows complete and timely information on government cash	59 (59%)	41 (41%)	-	-	-
2	IPSAS enables efficient cash management	46 (46%)	50 (50%)	4 (4%)	-	-
3	IPSAS reduces bank fees and transaction cost	8 (8%)	92 (92%)	-	-	-
4	IPSAS paves way for timely capture and payment of all due revenues into government coffers	39 (39%)	56 (56%)	-	3 (3%)	2 (2%)
5	IPSAS promote proper monitoring , inflow and out flow of expenses of government	30 (30%)	70 (70%)	-	-	-

Source: Field Survey 2022

59 (59%) of respondents strongly agree that IPSAS provides complete and timely information on government cash, while 41 (41%) disagree. Furthermore, 46 (46%) of respondents strongly agree that IPSAS allows for efficient cash management, 50 (50%) agree, and 4 (4%) are undecided. This demonstrates that when IPSAS is used, the majority of respondents believe in cash usage transparency. The vast majority of respondents (92%) agree that IPSAS reduces bank fees and transaction costs, with eight percent (8%) strongly agreeing (Table 3). According to the above table's results, 39(39%) of respondents believe that IPSAS allows for the timely capture and payment of all due revenues into government coffers; 56(56%) agree; 3(3%) disagree; and 2(2%) strongly disagree. As a result, a greater proportion of respondents agree that it provides timely information on all owed revenues to the government. IPSAS promotes proper government expense monitoring, inflow and outflow, according to 30 (30%) of respondents, while 70 (70%) strongly agreed.

3.4. Impacts of IPSAS on transparency of public Funds in government organization

Table 4: Impacts of IPSAS on transparency of public Funds in government organization

S/N	Statement	No. of Respondents/ Percentage (%)				
		SA	A	U	D	SD
1	IPSAS promotes transparency by preventing the misuse of government funds.	49 (49%)	51 (51%)	-	-	-
2	IPSAS ensure proper cash management by removing idle funds that are typically held by various commercial banks.	90 (90%)	10 (10%)	-	-	-
3	IPSAS aids in the detection of multiple accounts operated by government MDAs.	26 (26%)	64 (64%)	5 (5%)	5 (5%)	15 (15%)
4	IPSAS have ensured transparency in the public sector's financial management.	76 (76%)	24 (24%)	-	-	-
5	IPSAS ensure that government transactions are clear.	45 (45%)	55 (55%)	-	-	-

Source: Field Survey 2022

Table 4 shows that 49(49%) of respondents strongly agree that IPSAS promotes transparency by preventing misappropriation of government funds, while 51(51%) agree. 90% agree that IPSAS ensure proper cash management by eliminating idle funds typically held by different commercial banks, while 10% disagree. According to the respondents' mixed feelings, 26(26%) strongly agree that IPSAS helps reduce the occurrence of multiple accounts operated by government MDAs, 64(64%) agree, 5(5%) are undecided, 5(5%) disagree, and another 5(5%) strongly disagree. According to the data in the table above, 76(76%) of respondents strongly agree that IPSAS has improved transparency in financial management in the public sector, while 24(24%) disagree. IPSAS ensures clarity in government transactions, according to 45 (45%) and 55 (55%), respectively.

3.5. Testing of Hypotheses

The Wilcoxon statistical test tool was used to test the linear relationship between the dependent and independent variables using SPSS version 20 as shown in the tables below:

3.5.1. Hypothesis 1

Ho1: IPSAS Adoption has no significant effect on the Accountability in Nigerian Public Sector

Table 5: The Impact of IPSAS Adoption on Nigerian Public Sector Accountability

Null Hypothesis	Test	Significance	Decision
The median difference between Accountability Prior to IPSAS Adoption and Accountability Following IPSAS Adoption equals 0.	Wilcoxon Signed Rank Test Samples	0.045	Reject the null hypothesis

The hypothesis one result in table 5 above indicates that there is a significant difference in the accountability of the Nigerian public sector before and after the adoption of IPSAS. Despite having a P-value of 0.045, which is less than the 5% significance threshold, the test is statistically significant. The null hypothesis was rejected, and the alternate hypothesis, that IPSAS adoption has a significant effect on accountability in Nigerian public-sector organizations, was accepted.

This study is similar to that of Ogbuagu and Onuora (2019), who investigated the impact of international public sector accounting standards (IPSAS) adoption on responsibility and transparency in Nigerian public sector organizations, using the Anambra State ministry of finance as a case study. According to their research findings, the adoption of international public sector accounting standards has had a significant impact on accountability in Nigerian public sector organizations. Similarly, the findings of this study agree with those of Ijeoma (2015), who assessed the impact of International Public Sector Accounting Standards (IPSAS) on the reliability, credibility, and integrity of financial reporting in Nigerian state government administrations and concluded that IPSAS adoption has positively impacted and intruded integrity in Nigerian public sector organizations.

3.5.2. Hypothesis 2

Ho2: IPSAS Adoption has no significant effect on Transparency of Nigerian Public Sector

Table 6: The Impact of IPSAS Adoption on Nigerian Public Sector Transparency.

Null Hypothesis	Test	Significance	Decision
The median difference in transparency before and after IPSAS adoption equals 0.	Wilcoxon Signed Rank V Test Related Samples	0.043	Reject the null hypothesis

The results of hypothesis two in table 6 show that there is a significant difference in the transparency of the Nigerian public sector before and after the adoption of IPSAS. Despite a P-value of 0.043, which is less than the 5% cutoff, the test is statistically significant. The null hypothesis was rejected, and the alternate hypothesis, that IPSAS adoption has a significant effect on transparency in Nigerian government organizations, was accepted.

The preceding findings are related to the work of Ogbuagu and Onuora (2019), who investigated the impact of international public sector accounting standards (IPSAS) adoption on accountability and transparency in Nigerian public sector organizations, using the Anambra State ministry of finance as a case study. According to their findings, the adoption of international public sector accounting standards has had a significant impact on transparency in Nigerian public sector organizations. This supports the findings of Ijeoma and Oghoghomeh (2014), who investigated the expectations, benefits, and challenges of adopting International Public Sector Accounting Standards (IPSAS) in Nigeria. The study did find, however, that the adoption of IPSAS is expected to increase transparency in Nigeria's public sector.

4. CONCLUSION

The purpose of the study was to evaluate the impact of IPSAS on the financial accountability of selected federal MDAs in Oyo State, Nigeria. According to the findings of the study, implementing IPSAS improves accountability, transparency, and reduces corruption in the selected local governments. According to the study's findings, the adoption of IPSAS is expected to increase the level of accountability and transparency in Nigeria's public sector, as well as provide more meaningful information to decision makers and improve the quality of Nigeria's financial reporting system. As a result, the adoption of IPSAS in Nigeria is expected to improve operating procedures and reporting practices, thereby strengthening good governance and relationships with both the government and the governed.

Following the study's findings, the following recommendations were made:

- i. To maintain and sustain enhanced credibility of financial statements by public sector entities, governments at all levels must engage in continuous training and retraining of accounting personnel charged with the responsibilities of preparing the accounts.
- ii. The Federal Government should enact an enabling law to support the adoption and implementation of IPSAS, as well as institute appropriate sanctions to ensure full compliance.
- iii. Governments must consider enacting relevant legislation to protect and enable whistleblowers, and these laws must be backed up by appropriate sanctions to ensure full compliance.
- iv. Governments should develop plans for a smooth and rapid transition to full accrual-based IPSAS in order to maximize the perceived benefits of accrual-based IPSAS.
- v. The government should enforce the adoption of IPSAS because it has significantly improved and enhanced the level of accountability and transparency in public sector organizations.

- vi. For accountability to be successfully entrenched in public offices in Nigeria, there must be a reduction in the level of corruption, improved public sector accounting and auditing standards, legislators taking positions as champions of accountability, and a total restructure of public accounts committees.

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